

Mutual Fund in India- A Study

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Abstract

An attempt is presented in this article to explain about Mutual fund in India. The mutual fund industry started in India in a small way with the UTI act, planning what was effectively a tiny savings division within the RBI. Over 25 years this grew fairly successfully and gave investors of good return and therefore in 1989 as the next logical step, financial institutions and public sector banks were allowed to float mutual fund, and their success encouraged the government to allow the private sector to foray into this area.

Keywords: UTI- Unit Trust of India, SEBI- Security Exchange Board of India, RBI- Reserve Bank of India.

The mutual fund industry ignited in India in a small way with the UTI act, planning what was effectively a tiny savings division within the RBI. Over 25 years this grew fairly successfully and gave investors of good return and therefore in 1989 as the next logical step, financial institutions and public sector banks were allowed to float mutual fund, and their success encouraged the government to allow the private sector to foray into this area. In 1963, the day the concept of Mutual Fund took birth in India. The unit trust of India invited investors or rather to those who believed in savings, to park their money in UTI mutual fund. For 30 year its goal without a single second player. Though in the year 1988 saw new mutual fund companies, UTI remained in a monopoly position.

The appearance of mutual funds in India in the initial phase was not even close to a satisfactory level. People unusually understood, and of course, investing was out of the question. But yes 24 million shareholders were accustomed to guaranteed high returns by the beginning of liberalization of the industry in 1992 this good records of UTI became a marketing tool for new entrants.

The Net Asset Value (NAV) of mutual fund in India declined when stock prices started falling in the year 1992. Those days the market regulation did not allow portfolio shifts into alternative investment. There was instead no choice apart from holding the cash or to further continue investing in shares — one more thing to be noted. Since only closed-end funds continued floated in the market, the investors disinvested by marketing at a loss in the secondary market.

SEBI came out with comprehensive regulation in 1993, which defined the structure of the mutual fund, including asset management companies for the first time. The supervisory authority adopted a set

of measures to create a transparent, also competitive environment in mutual funds. Some of them were like relaxing investment limitations into the market, the introduction of open-ended funds and paving the gateway during mutual funds to launch a pension scheme. The measures were taken to make mutual funds the critical instrument for long term savings. The more the quality offered, the quantitative will be investors.

Several private sectors mutual funds obtained launched in 1993 and 1994. The share of individual players has risen rapidly since then. As long as mutual fund companies are making with lower risks and higher profitability in a short period, more and more people will be inclined to invest until and unless mutual funds. The mutual fund industry has seen a lot of changes in the past few years with multinational companies. I am coming into the country, bringing in their professional expertise in managing funds worldwide. In the past few years, there has been a consolidation phase going on in the mutual fund industry in India. Now investors have a wide range of scheme to choose from depending on their profiles.

A mutual fund is financial intermediaries who collect the savings of investors and invest them in an extensive and well-diversified portfolio of securities such as money market instruments, corporate and government bonds and equity share of joint stock companies. Mutual funds can survive and thrive only if they can live up to the hopes and trusts of their members.

Phases of Mutual Funds

First phase 1964-1987

- 1964 to 1987: UTI was established in 1963 by an act of parliament
- That was set up by the RBI and functioned under the regulatory and administrative control of the RBI
- In 1978 UTI was de-linked from the RBI and the Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI) obtained over the supervisory also an executive authority in place of RBI
- The primary scheme launched by UTI was unit scheme 1964 at the end of 1988 UTI had Rs 6700 crores of assets

Second Phase 1987-1993(Entry of public sector funds)

- 1987 listed the entry of non-UTI, public sector mutual funds set by the Public Sector Banks and General Insurance Corporation of India (GIC) and Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC)
- SBI Mutual fund obtained the first non-UTI mutual fund established in June 1987 developed by Canara Bank mutual fund (Dec 1989), Indian Bank mutual fund (Nov 1989), Bank of India (June 1990), Bank of Baroda mutual fund (Oct 1992)
- LIC established its mutual fund in June 1989 while GIC must set up its mutual fund in Dec 1990
- At the end of 1993, the mutual fund industry became an asset under Management of Rs 47,004 crores.

Third Phase 1993-2003 (Entry of Private sector funds)

- With the entry of private sector funds in 1993 a new era started in the Indian Mutual Fund Industry, giving the Indian investors a more extensive choice of fund families, also 1993 was the year in which the 1st mutual fund regulations came into being, following which all mutual funds, except UTI, were to be registered and governed.
- The erstwhile Kothari Pioneer (now merged by Franklin Templeton) was the First private sector mutual fund listed in July 1993

- The 1993 SEBI (Mutual Fund) regulation obtained substituted by a more comprehensive and revised mutual fund regulations in 1996. The industry now functions under the SEBI (Mutual Fund) regulations 1996
- The number of MF houses went on increasing with many Foreign MF producing up funds in India, and also the industry has witnessed several mergers and acquisitions.
- As at the end of January 2003, there were 33MF with a total asset of Rs 1,21,805 crores
- The UTI with Rs 44,541 crores of assets under management was way ahead of other MF.

Fourth Phase- February 2003 – April 2014

- In Feb 2003, following the repeal of the UTI act 1963, UTI was bifurcated into two separate things. One is the Specified Undertaking of the UTI by assets under management of Rs 29,835 crores as at the end of January 2003 describing broadly, the assets of US 64 scheme, assured return and specific other systems.
- The particularized undertaking of UTI, functioning under an administrator and the rules framed by the government of India also does not come under the purview of the mutual fund regulation.
- The second is the UTI mutual fund Ltd, sponsored by LIC and SBI; it is registered with SEBI and functions under the mutual fund regulations.
- With the bifurcation of the erstwhile UTI and several mergers taking place among several private sector funds, the MF industry entered its fourth phase of consolidation.

Following the global meltdown in the year 2009, security markets all over the world had tanked, and so was the case in India. Most investors who had opened the capital market during the peak had lost money, and their faith in MF products was significantly shaken. The abolition of entry load by SEBI linked with the after-effects of the global financial crisis, depend the adverse impact on the Indian MF industry, which struggled to recover and remodel itself for over 2years, in an attempt to maintain its economic viability which is evident from the sluggish growth in MF industry AVM between 2010 to 2013

Fifth Phase- Since May 2014

- Taking cognizance of the absence of penetration of MF's especially in tier II and tier III cities and the need for greater alignment of the interest of different stakeholders, SEBI introduced several progressive measures in September 2012 to "Re-energize" the Indian MF industry and increase MF's penetration.
- In due course, the measures did succeed in reversing the negative trend that had set in after global meltdown and increased significantly after the new government was formed at the center.
- Since May 2014 the industry has witnessed steady inflows and improvement in the AUM as well as the number of investor folio's(accounts)
- The industry AUM crossed the milestone of Rs 10 Trillion(RS 10 lakh crore) for the first time as on 31st may 2014, and in a short span of 2 years the AUM size crossed Rs 15 lakh crores in July 2016
- The overall size of the Indian MF industry has developed from Rs 3.26 Trillion as on 31st March 2007 to Rs 15.63 Trillion as on 31st August 2016, the largest AUM ever and a five-fold improvement in a span of less than 10years.
- The MF, industry has more increased its AUM in the last four years from Rs 5.87 trillion as on 31st March 2012 to 12.33 trillion as on 31st March 2016 and extra grown to Rs 15.63 trillion as on 31st August 2016

- The number of investor folios has gone up from 3.95crores folio's as on 31/03/2014 to 4.98crores as on 31/08/2016
- On an average 3.38 lakh, new folio's are added every month in the last 2years since June 2014

The growth in the size of the industry has been possible due to the twin effects of the regulatory measures taken by SEBI in re-energizing the MF industry in September 2012 and the supporter from mutual fund distributors in expanding the local base.

MF distributors have also had a significant role in popularizing systematic investment plans (SIP) over the years. In April 2016, the number of SIP accounts had crossed 1crores mark, and currently each month retail investor contribute around Rs 3,500crores via sips. Thus Mutual Fund in India is reviewed in the five phases in India.

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